

Map of events in Pishpek uezd from July 4th to August 23rd in 1916*

VERNY
(ALMATY)

PISHPEK
(BISHKEK)

Belovodskoe v.

Aleksandronovskoe v.

Tokmok v.

Pokrovka v.

Samsonovskaya station
(Boroldoi)

Jel-Aryk
post station

Chui
hydrometric station

Novorossiskoe v.
(Shabdan)

Suusamyr
hydrometric station

Jumgal
hydrometric station

Belotsarskoe v.
(Kuiruchuk)

Legend

- Events of August 7-11
- Events of August 12-14
- Events of August 15-23
- Black color – actions by Russian imperial forces
- White color – actions by rebels
- Uezd center
- Village of Russian settlers
- State bordert
- Uezd border
- Action of punitive squads
- Siege or battle
- Massacre or murder of Russians
- Massacre or murder of Kyrgyz
- Opium cultivation site
- An event with peaceful outcome
- Hotbed of rebellion

* Dates according pre-revolutionary calendar

